

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for African and European **Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D6.8 Electronic newsletter – Third Release

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Executive Summary

Youthmakers Hub, with the contribution of all partners, has produced the third newsletter; more will follow, one every semester. The newsletter was circulated in an electronic format to the interested public through the Mailchimp platform, and it was also uploaded to the official project webpage (<https://africoneu.eu/newsletter/>). The third newsletter of the project was released and sent on the 22nd of July 2022. A database with e-mails has been developed during the last months with all people subscribed to our newsletter. 500 people received the newsletter. Three main categories have been included in the newsletter: Opportunities & News, Completed AfriConEU activities & Coming-up.

Besides disseminating our third newsletter through the Mailchimp platform and the AfriConEU Website, it was also published through the AfriConEU LinkedIn Page, expanding our digital audience and community and boosting our brand awareness, building credibility and generating leads to our social media pages.

The published issue illustrated the achievements reached during the reported period regarding the project's developments and peripheral activities, such as participation in external events. Part of the newsletter was the AfriConEU Networking Academy, the launch of the Brokerage Event, and the brand new AfriConEU Vidcast Series, Digital Innovation Talks. Given the importance of the newsletter, concise, clear and straightforward sentences are essential to spark and sustain interest in readers on the project.

AfriConEU Newsletter #3 | July 2022

Welcome to our third newsletter. We've missed you!

Are you excited to learn what we have been doing over the last 6 months?

If you missed our previous newsletters, you could check them out [here](#).

Opportunities & News

Job Opportunity Tip-offs

Are you looking for a new job opening in Europe or Africa?

Make sure to check the following job openings. → [Read more](#)

Events Opportunity Alerts

Are you interested in participating in cool, innovative, entrepreneurial, and business events?

Don't miss any of them. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU in the Press

In case you missed our fourth **Press Release**, "Trans-Continental Interactions in the Digital Innovation Ecosystem," you can access it [here](#).

For publications in the **media**, check us out [here](#).

AfriConEU Networking Academy

Our Networking Academy is finally on, connecting and sharing best practices, experiences, and resources between DIHs in Africa and Europe.

We kicked off on May 12th, 2022, in Tanzania, with [Buni](#) implementing a workshop on purpose-driven digital innovation hubs as part of the Innovation Week Tanzania. → [Read more](#)

Africa-Europe Week 2022

We participated in the Africa-Europe Week 2022 in Brussels on February 14th-18th, 2022. We contributed to the discussion for the Joint Vision for 2030 related to the Digital Transition and trans-continental collaboration. → [Read more](#)

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Completed AfriConEU Activities

AfriConEU Networking Academy Events

We have already implemented 9 events exploring various topics, including **DIH strategy and resources, sustainable business models and impact, gender finance gap, and inclusive ecosystem building**. Our events have digital, hybrid, and in-person formats, making sure they are accessible to our audience in Africa and Europe. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU Research

Our team presented the paper "Intercontinental Cooperation to foster the Capacity of European and African Digital Innovation Hubs to accelerate the Digital transition – The AfriConEU project" during the 16th annual International Technology, Education and Development Conference, **INTED2022**, that took place online on March 7th & 8th 2022. → [Read more](#)

Development of the Trans-Continental Partnership | Online Workshop

Porto Business School organized the virtual workshop "Development of the Trans-Continental Partnership" on February 3rd, 2022. The workshop aimed to co-design a program based on the needs, opportunities, and recommendations of the Africa-Europe partnership. → [Read more](#)

Virtual Stakeholders' Engagement Session | Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda, Tanzania

Emerging Communities for Africa organized a **Virtual Stakeholders' Engagement Session** for Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda, and Tanzania on February 23rd, 2022. The engagement session aimed to identify challenges and opportunities to strengthen DIHs, ensuring seamless collaboration between stakeholders. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU Vidcast Series | Digital Innovation Talks

"Digital Innovation Talks" is the theme of our brand new "AfriConEU Vidcast Series," which includes 12 monthly episodes for April 2022 - March 2023 exploring different topics related to the EU-African Digital Innovation Hubs and Startup Ecosystems. If you don't want to miss any episode, subscribe to our [Youtube Channel](#) and check out the first 4 episodes.

ICT-58 Family Project Meetings & Networking

We stay in contact with our family projects and relevant initiatives, exchange ideas, and network further to achieve our shared objectives. In this framework, we met virtually during the last months with DIGILOGIC, HUBiquitous, D4D Hub, AEDIB Net, mAKE, ENRICH in Africa, and BIC Africa. → [Read more](#)

Coming up

AfriConEU Networking Academy Events | Online, In-person & Hybrid

Check out our Academy's events that include workshops, webinars, masterclasses, conferences, and events relevant to Digital Innovation Hubs, Entrepreneurs, Tech Hubs, Start-ups, and Stakeholders for Africa and Europe.

Subscribe to our calendar and always stay up to date!

Brokerage Event | Hybrid - Online & Bologna, Italy

A two-day event to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing between the African and European Innovation Ecosystems.

About this event

The AfriConEU Brokerage Event will be hosted on November 2 and 3, 2022, in Bologna, Italy, with parallel events in Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania, and Uganda.

The two-day event will focus on three main activities:

- **Presenting** good practices in the African and European innovation ecosystems.
- **Networking** and **developing** strategic partnerships among the participants.
- **Identifying** challenges and opportunities connected to the work of AfriConEU.

Register Now

If you want to check about our project's latest updates, you can always see [what's new](#).

Stay tuned and follow us on [social media](#), as we will be sharing opportunities for Digital Innovation Hubs, Entrepreneurs, Investors, Institutions in the field of digital skills, or any other stakeholder interested in strengthening the EU-Africa innovation partnership!

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